

ETHNOBOTANICAL SURVEY AND PHYTOCONSTITUENTS OF PROMINENT MEDICINAL PLANT FOR CANCER MANAGEMENT IN COMMUNITIES BORDERING AKURE FOREST RESERVE, ONDO STATE, NIGERIA

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ABSTRACT

*Cancer cases in Nigeria are steadily on the rise, with thousands of new diagnoses reported annually. Cancer diagnosis is commonly linked with depression. This put the patients with advanced cases at risk of committing suicide. Despite decades of medical advancement, conventional treatment methods come with significant challenges. Many researchers had confirmed the success of herbal therapies, considering their affordability, accessibility, and lower toxicity in relation to other treatments. This study surveyed medicinal plants used for cancer management by herbal practitioners in eight communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve. The socio-demographic characteristics revealed that the respondents were predominantly female (59%), middle-aged (65%), fairly educated (62.5%), and dependent on farming (62.5%) as their mainsource of livelihood. Herbal practitioners in the study areas were knowledgeable about cancer (78.8%) and 4% had reported cases of cancer in their communities. A total of eight (8) medicinal plants for cancer management in communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve were discovered. The results of phytoconstituents of *Annona muricata*, the prominent medicinal plant, revealed its efficacy in cancer management as it contains a higher concentration of phytate (451.29mg/g), a natural compound that lowers the risk of cancer disease. In this study, a plantation of *Annona muricata* was established in the Federal University of Technology Akure (FUTA). Further studies on the development of more efficacious products for cancer management using *Annona muricata* are recommended.*

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INTRODUCTION

There are indications that cancer is a deadly disease that has resulted in the death of many people across the World. World Health Organisation (WHO, 2022) stressed that cancer is one of the leading causes of death globally, claiming nearly 10 million lives in 2020 alone. Cancer is not only a health crisis but also a socio- economic burden, affecting individuals, families, and communities. Cancer cases in Nigeria are steadily increasing, with thousands of new diagnoses reported annually (Federal Ministry of Health, 2018). The Nigerian National Cancer Control Plan (2018–2022) noted that cancer is responsible for over 72,000 deaths each year in the country, with breast, cervical, and prostate cancers being the most common (Federal Ministry of Health, 2018).

Despite decades of medical advancement, conventional treatment methods such as chemotherapy, radiotherapy, and surgical removal of tumors still come with significant challenges. Many of these methods are costly, especially in developing countries, and often cause unpleasant side effects such as fatigue, hair loss, immune suppression, and damage to healthy cells (Newman & Cragg, 2020). These realities have created a growing interest in alternative or complementary therapies, especially those derived from natural products like medicinal plants.

Many cultures have utilized medicinal plants for centuries to treat and prevent illness. They are known to contain naturally occurring chemical compounds (phytochemicals) that can have anticancer properties (Shahi & Singh, 2025). Over the years, some plant-derived compounds have been developed into standard anticancer drugs, such as vincristine from *Catharanthus roseus* and paclitaxel from *Taxus brevifolia* (Rates, 2001). These successes have reinforced the idea that nature remains a valuable source of potential cancer-fighting agents.

Nigeria is richly blessed with an abundance of medicinal plants, many of which are found within its forest reserves. Traditional practitioners across different communities have long relied on these medicinal plants to treat several ailments, including symptoms and conditions related to cancer. However, despite their popularity at the grassroots level, no known study has provided a catalogue of plants with anticancer properties in communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve, Ondo State.

Moreover, overexploitation of wild medicinal plants without proper cultivation practices poses a threat to their continued existence. This is where domestication, the process of cultivating wild plant species in controlled environments, becomes essential. Domestication not only ensures a consistent and sustainable supply of these plants for research and therapeutic purposes, it also reduces pressure on natural populations, helping to conserve biodiversity.

This study, therefore, focuses on ethnobotanical survey and domestication of most populous medicinal plant in cancer management for further study and development of efficacious products for cancer management in Nigeria.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Area

This study was carried out in Akure Forest Reserve (Fig 1). Akure forest reserve is located in Akure South Local Government Area and Forest Reserve covers an area of 6,993 ha. It is located between the latitudes of 7°11'40" to 7°21'60"N and the longitudes of 5°00'00" to 5°04'80". Akintunde-Alo and Akomolafe (2022) revealed that the mean daily temperatures in this reserve range from 21°C to 29°C, and the annual rainfall averages 2000mm. The reserve is surrounded with communities that depend directly and indirectly on the reserve for sustainable livelihood. Prominent among the communities are: Kolawole, Aponmu, and Obadare. These communities are dominated with several tribes across Nigeria.

Figure 1: Map of Akure Forest Reserve

Source: Akintunde-Alo and Akomolafe, 2022

Method of Data Collection

Eight (8) rural communities bordering the reserve were selected purposefully. They include: Sasere, Obada, Kolawole, Gbokesoogun, Gberedu, Kajola, Aponmu, and Obadare (Figure 2). These communities were selected because they are homes to many herbal practitioners who are custodians of indigenous medicinal knowledge. A total of eighty (80) copies of semi-structured questionnaire were administered to herbal practitioners across the eight communities. Purposive sampling was used because medicinal knowledge is specialized and restricted to practitioners. A prominent plant (*Annona muricata*) used for cancer management in the study area was identified and its phytochemical constituents were analyzed. This analysis was done according to Association of Official Analytical Chemists (AOAC) standard as described in Lawal *et al.* (2023). The phytochemical constituents determined include: saponin, alkaloid, terpenoid, Tannin, cardenolides, cardiac glycosides, anthraquinone contents, phytate and oxalate.

Figure 2: Map of the Study Area with the Selected Communities

Data Analysis

Data from ethnobotanical survey was subjected to statistical analysis using IBM statistical package for social science (SPSS) version 25.0 and the results are presented as charts, frequency and percentage.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Results

Demographic Characteristics of Respondents

The demographic characteristics of respondents are presented in Table 1. The study revealed that women were more involved in the use of medicinal plants as 41.3% of the respondents were male, while 58.8% were female. Majority of the respondents were in their economically active age because 65% were between 31 and 50 years. In terms of marital status, about two-thirds (67.5%) of the respondents were married, while 18.8% were single.

With respect to education, 62.5% of respondents had some form of formal education, with 23.8% attaining secondary education and 13.8% having tertiary education. The average family size of the respondents was 4 persons, with 62.5% of respondents had between 3–5 household members. Although the respondents were herbal practitioners, the study confirms that farming (62.5%) remains their central occupation.

Table 1: Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

Demographic Variable	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender		
Male	33	41.3
Female	47	58.8
Age		
≤30 years	21	26.3
31–40 years	32	40.0
41–50 years	20	25.0
>50 years	7	8.8
Marital Status		
Single	15	18.8
Married	54	67.5
Polygamy	6	7.5
Widowed	3	3.8
Divorced	2	2.5
Education Level		
No Formal Education	30	37.5
Primary Education	20	25.0
Secondary Education	19	23.8
Tertiary Education	11	13.8
Family Size		
1–2 members	18	22.5
3–5 members	50	62.5
6–10 members	12	15.0
Primary Occupation		
Farming	50	62.5
Trading	18	22.5
Artisan	8	10.0
Civil Service	4	5.0

Knowledge and Awareness of Cancer in the Study Areas

The study revealed that majority of respondents (78.8%) were aware of cancer disease (Fig. 2) and 4% of respondents reported some cancer cases in their community, while the overwhelming majority (96%) claimed that no cancer cases had been reported in their communities (Fig. 3). More so, the study revealed that majority of the respondents who had knowledge of cancer disease in the study area

(88.5%) confirmed the use and efficacy of *Annona muricata* for cancer treatment. According to the respondents, this plant could cure cancer disease if used according to the instruction of the herbal practitioners.

Figure2: Respondents' Awareness of Cancer Disease in the Study Areas

Figure 3: Recorded Cancer Cases in the Study Areas

This study indicated that free areas and farm land were the major sources of medicinal plants, with less reliance on protected areas. A large proportion of the respondents (70%) harvested medicinal plants from free areas (open fields or uncultivated land). About 20% relied on their farmland for medicinal plants, while 10% of the respondent harvested from the forest reserve (Table 2). Continuous availability of medicinal plants for cancer management and other ailments was guaranteed through domestication (88.75%) and sustainable harvesting (11.25%) as presented in Table 3. In this study, a total of eight (8) medicinal plants were discovered and used by the respondents for cancer management in the study areas (Table 4). Prominent among the listed medicinal plants include: *Annona muricata*, *Azadirachta indica* and *Bryophyllum pinnatum*.

The phytoconstituents in *Annona muricata* leaf is presented in Table 5. Among the phytoconstituents present in the leaf of *Annona muricata*, Alkaloid was discovered to have the highest percentage (1.99%). This followed by Saponin with a percentage of 0.47%. Phytate, a natural compound that offers an antioxidant benefits and potentially lowering risks for diseases like cancer, had the highest concentration (451.29mg/g) in the leaf of *Annona muricata* as presented in the Table.

Table 2: Location where Medicinal Plants were found and Harvested in the Study Areas

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Free Areas	56	70.00
Farmland	16	20.00
Forest Reserve	8	10.00

Table 3: Ways to ensure Availability of Medicinal Plants in the Study Areas

Response	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Domestication	71	88.75
Sustainable Harvesting	9	11.25

Table 4: Medicinal Plants for Cancer Management in the Study Areas

Scientific Name	Common Name	Habit	Rank (%)
<i>Annona muricata</i>	Soursop	T	88.5
<i>Azadirachta indica</i>	Neem	T	3.5
<i>Bryophyllum pinnatum</i>	Life Plant / Miracle Leaf	H	5.0
<i>Carica papaya</i>	Pawpaw / Papaya	H	1.0
<i>Mitracarpus villosus</i>	Tropical girdlepod	H	1.5
<i>Vernonia amygdalina</i>	Bitter leaf	S	0.5

Note: T – Tree, H – Herb, S - Shrub

Table 5: Phytoconstituents of *Annona muricata* leaf

Phytoconstituents	Values
Alkaloid (%)	1.99±0.11
Saponin (%)	0.47±0.04
Terpenoid (mg/g)	4.11±0.21
Tannin (mg/g)	1.79±0.15
Cardiac Glycoside (mg/g)	1.23±0.10
Oxalate (mg/g)	20.07±2.01
Cardenolide (mg/g)	0.15±0.01
Anthraquinone (mg/g)	1.35±0.01
Phytate (mg/g)	451.29±12.11

Discussion

Cancer disease is caused by wild division of abnormal cells in a part of the body. Abnormal cells arise from a complex interaction of genetic, environmental, and lifestyle factors (Bryndin, 2025). Though there are many types of cancer ranging from prostate cancer, lung cancer, cervical cancer, leukaemia and colorectum to liver cancer, kidney cancer and ovary cancer, the name is associated with where the abnormal cell division occurs in human body. In Nigeria, cancer has been identified as one of the most deadly diseases and has been established to be a leading cause of death globally (Sung *et al.*, 2021). Cancer diagnosis is commonly associated with thoughts of death (Adiguna *et al.*, 2025). In advanced cancer patients, depression may facilitate the desire for hastened death (Rosenstein, 2011).

The use of modern day medicine for cancer treatment worldwide and Nigeria in particular is skyrocketing, making it more traumatic to low income earners and rural dwellers. However, Researchers have revealed the use of medicinal plants for prevention and management of several life threatened ailments such as breast cancer in humans (Sodiq *et al.*, 2025). More so, many studies had uncovered the success of herbal therapies vis-a-vis their affordability, easy accessibility, and lesser toxicity when compared with other treatments (Gurib-Fakim 2006, Cragg 2007; Ohiagu *et al.*, 2021). In this study, we discovered six medicinal plants used in cancer management by the herbal practitioners in communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve, Ondo State. *Annona muricata* was most prominent among the medicinal plants mentioned for cancer management in the study areas.

Majority of herbal practitioners in communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve were middle-aged and predominantly female. The reason for more women in the use of herbal remedy for cancer management in the study areas could be attributed to their peculiar role in ensuring healthy living of family members. This study is incongruent with the work of Aparicio *et al.* (2021) that women are more knowledgeable on edible and medicinal plants and also use more plants than men. Similarly, Gonza lez-Garrido *et al.* (2022) reported that women (94.7%) were predominantly involved in the use of medicinal plants to treat some disease in South American country. This finding is significant because women in many African rural communities play a central role in healthcare decision-making and are often custodians of traditional medicinal knowledge (Adefegha *et al.*, 2021).

We discovered that herbal practitioners in the study areas were also involved in other activities to make ends meet. This is because incomes from herbal practices do not come as regularly as possible and life could become unbearable if no patronage is recorded within a month. More so, relying solely on wild harvesting or external suppliers can lead to shortages or inconsistent quality. Farming guarantees a steady, reliable supply of the specific herbs they need for their practice. Some medicinal plants are rare and require specific growing environments; farming allows practitioners to cultivate these particular species. The dominance of farmers among respondents further emphasizes the

interconnection between agricultural practices and medicinal plant usage, as farming households tend to rely heavily on ethnobotanical resources for both primary healthcare and livelihood support (Kayode *et al.*, 2017). This pattern is the same with studies conducted in Nigeria and other parts of West Africa, where rural farmers and women have been identified as the major repositories of indigenous knowledge of medicinal plants (Akinmoladun *et al.*, 2020).

A high level of cancer awareness (79%) was observed among respondents, along with a widespread knowledge of plants used for other ailments. This indicates that local communities not only recognize cancer as a health challenge but also associate it with specific plant-based remedies. This finding supports the view that ethnomedicine remains an integral part of healthcare in sub-Saharan Africa, particularly where access to modern health services is limited (WHO, 2022). Similar ethnobotanical surveys in Nigeria and Ghana reported that rural populations demonstrate considerable knowledge of medicinal plants for chronic diseases, including cancer, hypertension, and diabetes (Oladunmoye and Kehinde, 2020; Asase *et al.*, 2019). This reinforces the importance of documenting and validating such knowledge to prevent its erosion and to support complementary cancer care strategies.

The predominance knowledge of *Annona muricata* in the management of cancer in the study area could be attributed to its efficacy. This assertion was strengthened by the results of the phytoconstituents analysis of *Annona muricata* leaf. The presence of alkaloid (1.99%) and the highest concentration of phytate (451.29mg/g), a natural compound that offers an antioxidant benefits and potentially lowering risks for diseases like cancer, could be one of the factors responsible for the efficacy of this plant for cancer treatment in the study area. This finding was corroborated by Samaratunga and Katuwavila (2024) that *Annonamuricata* contain some phytochemicals with anticancer properties.

CONCLUSION

Ethnobotanical survey was carried out within the communities bordering Akure Forest Reserve in Ondo State. The findings are organised into two main parts. The first part covers the socio-demographic characteristics of respondents, their knowledge and awareness of cancer. The second part focuses on farming and harvesting practices. The respondents were predominantly female, middle-aged, fairly educated, and dependent on farming as an alternate source of livelihood. Herbal practitioners in the study areas knew about cancer and had reported cases of cancer disease in most communities bordering the reserve. Also, this study provided the list of medicinal plants used for cancer management in these communities and *Annonamuricata* was most widely used. This study successful established a plantation of *Annonamuricata* in FUTA for further research on the development of efficacious products for cancer management in Nigeria. Further studies on reasons for more efficacious effect attributed to *A.muricata* in the study area are recommended.

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